

Relationship among School Safety, School Discipline and Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students in North Central Zone, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated relationship among school safety, school discipline, and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North Central Zone, Nigeria. The study adopted correlation research design. The population of the study consisted of 205,073 SS 2 students from public senior secondary school in North Central zone. The sample size of 1530 respondents from the targeted population was used for this study using the multistage sampling technique. Two research questions were answered and two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The instruments used to collect data were "School safety and discipline questioner" (SSADQ) Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) and English Language Achievement Test (ELAT). The three instruments were validated by experts which gave some logical validity indices of 0.83 for SSADQ, 0.86 for MAT and 0.82 for ELAT. The reliability coefficient yielded 0.82 for SCQ and EDQ, 0.78 for MAT and 0.77 for ELAT. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was used to answer and analyze research questions on the basis of the values of r (coefficient of correlation). The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The major findings among many from the study indicated that there is a significant relationship between school safety and academic achievement and there was a significant relationship between school discipline and academic achievement. Based on the findings, it was concluded that school discipline and school safety enhances students' achievement. It was therefore recommended among many that school education stakeholders should pay close attention to the immediate needs in order for the desired outcome to be actualized.

Keywords: School safety, School discipline, Academic achievement, Senior secondary, School students.

Introduction

Education remains a fundamental tool for improving the worth, skills, knowledge, and overall development of individuals, while also advancing the socio-economic progress of society. As a transformative enterprise, education is continuously monitored and assessed to determine the extent to which its predetermined objectives are being achieved by learners. At any given time and place, the aim of education is geared toward engendering positive behavioural changes in learners and enhancing educational outcomes through quality academic achievement (Kolade et al., 2022). Academic achievement represents the measurable learning outcomes of instructional processes and indicates the degree to which students have attained curriculum-based expectations. Olumide (2025) describes academic achievement as the ability to study, retain facts, and communicate acquired knowledge either orally or in writing.

English Language and Mathematics remain core subjects for all learners regardless of their preferred vocation or career path. Their centrality derives from their capacity to support the understanding of other subjects through linguistic competence, logical reasoning, and quantitative skills (Kolade, 2023). Despite this importance, persistent declines in students' achievement in these foundational subjects have generated considerable concern among stakeholders in the education sector. Consequently, researchers, policymakers, and educators have called for empirical investigations to understand the underlying factors and propose effective interventions. As part of these efforts, government and non-governmental stakeholders have introduced various initiatives to strengthen the teaching and learning of Mathematics and English Language (Agborbet et al., 2020).

Recent studies have identified multiple school-related factors that may contribute to low learning outcomes. For instance, Nwobodo and Agusiobo (2022) highlighted the role of school safety and discipline in shaping learners' achievement. Adeyemi and Oduwole (2022) further asserted that both discipline and physical safety are essential school attributes that influence students' engagement, teachers' effectiveness, and the overall appeal of the school environment. School discipline, defined as the set of actions enforced to maintain organizational standards and ensure order (Mukamusana, 2017), plays a crucial role in regulating student behaviour. According to Weli and Nnaa (2020), clearly articulated rules and consistent enforcement of regulations are vital for creating an orderly school environment conducive to learning.

Empirical findings support the relevance of discipline in determining academic outcomes. In a study conducted in Rivers State, Weli and Nnaa (2020) found that the availability and enforcement of disciplinary rules significantly enhanced students' academic performance. Similarly, school safety has been identified as a key determinant of students' learning experiences. Abubakar (2022) noted that a safe school—free from violence and threats to life—provides a supportive environment for academic activities. In a related cross-country investigation, Shahriar et al. (2018) examined the effect of school safety on academic achievement among primary school students in Rwanda, Tanzania, and Zambia. Their findings revealed that school safety exerted a significant positive influence on academic outcomes across the three countries.

Collectively, these studies underscore the interrelated roles of school discipline and school safety in fostering academic achievement. A disciplined and safe school environment enhances student engagement, reduces disruptions, and promotes effective teaching and learning (Abubakar, 2022). Against this backdrop, the present study investigates the relationship between school safety, school discipline, and academic achievement among senior secondary school students in the North-Central Zone of Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between school safety of students' and academic achievement in mathematics and English language of senior secondary school students in North central zone, Nigeria?
2. What is the relationship between school discipline and academic achievement in mathematics and English language of senior secondary school students in North central zone, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between school safety and academic achievement in mathematics and English language of senior secondary school students in North central zone, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant relationship between school discipline and academic achievement in mathematics and English language of senior secondary school students in North central zone, Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the theories of threat assessment theory propounded by Gavin de Becker, a security expert in 1997 and positive behavioural interventions theories propounded by Dr, George Sugai and Dr. Robert Horner. The threat assessment theory emphasized the importance of recognizing and responding to potential security threats. The theory further assesses the seriousness and likelihood of such threats and further develops strategies for managing such threats. This theory is relevant to the school system by ensuring that potential threats to smooth teaching and learning in the school system is curbed by creating a safe and conducive learning environment. The positive behavioural interventions theory is a proactive approach to improving students' behaviour and academic achievement through effective teaching and reinforcement of positive behaviours. When applied to the school system, the theory is crucial in establishing a positive school culture in terms students' discipline. Furthermore, it

reduces the behavioural disruptions and increases students' engagement in learning as well as their academic achievement

Methodology

The study adopted a correlation research design. The main emphasis in a correlation study is to discover or establish the existence of a relationship or association or interdependence between two or more aspects of a situation. This design was considered suitable for this study because it provides the researcher the opportunity of obtaining the sample opinion of the population so as to infer the opinion of the entire population. The population for this study comprises of 205,073 SSII students from the six (6) states in North Central, Nigeria; namely: Benue, Kogi, Kwara, Niger, Plateau, and Nasarawa. The sample size of 1530 respondents was used for this study using the Research Advisors (2006) based on the 95% confidence interval. The study employed multi-stage sampling procedure in the selection of respondents from the sampled states of Benue, Plateau and Nasarawa. Three instruments used for this study were developed by the researcher and they include School safety and school discipline Questionnaire (SSASDQ), Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) and English Language Achievement Test (ELAT). The instruments were therefore validated by the experts. Cronbach Alpha was used to compute reliability coefficient, which yielded 0.84 for (SCQ) and (EDQ), Kuder-richardson reliability method was used for MAT and ELAT, reliability coefficient was 0.78 for MAT and 0.77 for ELAT. The research questions were answered using the calculated r-values of Pearson's product moment correlation while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance by comparing the p-value (probability values) of Pearson's Product Moment Correlation obtained from SPSS application with the significance level at 0.05. Hypotheses whose p-values were less than 0.05, were rejected while hypotheses whose p-values were greater than 0.05 were accepted.

Results and Discussion

Research Questions 1

What is the relationship between student physical safety and academic achievement in mathematics and English language of senior secondary school students of North central zone, Nigeria?

Table 1. Relationship between students School Safety and Academic Achievement in senior secondary schools in North Central zone, Nigeria.

Variables	N		Std. Dev.	r
School Safety	1530	26.49	5.66	0.479
Academic Achievement	1530	51.76	4.06	

Table 1 shows the relationship between school safety and academic achievement in senior secondary schools in North Central zone, Nigeria. The result revealed that school safety had ($= 26.49$) and academic achievement had ($= 51.76$). The study further revealed a moderate correlation value ($r = 0.479$) between school safety and students' academic achievement. This implies that there is a positively low relationship between school safety and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North Central Nigeria.

Research Questions 2

What is the relationship between school discipline and academic achievement in mathematics and English language of senior secondary school students in North Central, Nigeria?

Table 2. Relationship between School Discipline and Academic Achievement in senior secondary schools in North Central zone, Nigeria.

Variables	N		Std. Dev.	r
School Discipline	1530	23.80	7.68	0.934
Academic Achievement	1530	51.76	4.06	

Table 6 shows the relationship between school discipline and academic achievement in senior secondary schools in North Central zone, Nigeria. The result revealed that students' physical safety had ($= 23.80$) and academic achievement had ($= 51.76$). The result revealed a very high correlation value of ($r = 0.934$) between school discipline and students' academic achievement. This implies that there is a positively strong relationship between school discipline and academic achievement senior secondary school students in North Central Nigeria.

Testing of the Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between school safety and academic achievement in Mathematics and English language of senior secondary school students of North Central, Nigeria.

Table 3. Significance of Relationship between School Safety and Academic Achievement of Public Senior Secondary School Students in North Central, Nigeria.

Variables	N	r	Sig.(2-tailed)	Decision
School Safety*	1530	0.479	.018	Reject H_{01}
Academic Achievement	1530			

Level of significance Alpha (α) < 0.05 shows significant relationship

Table 3 reveals significance of relationship between school safety condition and academic Achievement of senior secondary school students in North Central, Nigeria. The result is given as $N = 1530$, $r = 0.479$, (p -value = 0.018). Since the p -value is less than 0.05, the hypothesis 1 is rejected implying there is a significant relationship between school safety condition and academic Achievement of senior secondary school students in North Central, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between school discipline and academic achievement in Mathematics and English language of senior secondary school students of North Central Nigeria.

Table 4. Relationship between school discipline and academic achievement of Public Senior Secondary School Students in North Central zone, Nigeria

Variables	N	r	Sig.(2-tailed)	Decision
School Discipline*	1530	0.934	.002	Reject
Academic Achievement	1530			H ₀₂

Level of significance Alpha (α) < 0.05 shows significant relationship

Table 3 reveals significance of relationship between school safety condition and academic Achievement of senior secondary school students in North Central, Nigeria. The result is given as N = 1530, r = 0.934, (p-value = 0.002). Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the hypothesis 2 is rejected implying there is a significant relationship between school discipline and academic Achievement of senior secondary school students in North Central, Nigeria.

Discussion of Results

Findings from hypothesis one revealed that there is a significant relationship between school safety condition and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North Central zone, Nigeria. This is corroborated with the Study by This is in line with Shahriar et al. (2018) which showed significant effects of school Safety on academic achievement in Rwanda, Tanzania and Gambia.

Finding based on hypothesis two revealed that there is a significant relationship between school discipline and academic achievement in Mathematics and English language of senior secondary school students in North central zone, Nigeria. Study by Weli, and Nnaa, (2020) which indicated there was significant impact of discipline on students' academic performance in public junior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Conclusion

The study examined relationship among school climate, emotional disorder, and academic achievement of senior secondary school students of North Central Zone, Nigeria. Findings from the study revealed that there is a significant relationship between student school safety condition, school discipline and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North Central zone, Nigeria. there is a significant relationship between school discipline and academic achievement in Mathematics and English language of senior secondary school students in North central zone, Nigeria. To enhance improved students' achievement, the study recommended that Government and education stakeholders should pay close attention to the immediate needs of the school. The physical safety condition and security of the students are taken into consideration. Inadequacy and inappropriateness of the school

environment may only handicap academic performance and worsen their desire to learn. Thus, students and other school community members should not compromise the value and importance of preserving peace and participating in any worthwhile activities such enforcing laws and upholding them, which can boost the school security and safety of student life. School authority put appropriate and suitable measures together to check student's maladaptive behaviour and indiscipline, which in turn will improve and instill discipline on the students. If indiscipline will be controlled, desirable academic outcomes could be actualized.

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